

On a One Type of Zero-Over-Zero Form Limits

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Abstract. It is hard to evaluate some limits by only making use of L'Hôpital's rule. In this paper, we consider the way to evaluate a one type of zero-over-zero form limits which has form of

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{f(x) - a}{g(x)} \quad (1)$$

where where f and g are functions such that $\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} f(x) = a$ and $\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} g(x) = 0$. In conclusion, we found the way to evaluate a one type of zero-over-zero form limit:

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{f_1(x)f_2(x) \cdots f_n(x) - a_1a_2 \cdots a_n}{g(x)} \quad (2)$$

where g is a function such that $\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} g(x) = 0$ and $f_1, f_2, \dots, f_n$ ($n \in \mathbb{N}$) are functions such that, for every $k \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$, $\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} f_k(x) = a_k$ and $\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{f_k(x) - a_k}{g(x)}$ exists as sum of the same type of zero-over-zero form limits without making use of L'Hôpital's rule.

Keywords. Zero-Over-Zero Form Limits; L'Hôpital's rule; Limits; Derivative.

By making use of L'Hôpital's rule, we can calculate almost every 0/0 form limits like

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{e^{x^3}(x^2 + 4)^3 - 64}{x^2}. \quad (3)$$

However, limit such as

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{e^{x^3} \cos(2x)(x^2 + 4)^3 - 64}{x^2} \quad (4)$$

would be very complicated to calculate by only using L'Hôpital's rule.

Here, we consider a way, without making use of L'Hôpital's rule, to calculate the following one type of zero-over-zero form limits

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{f(x) - a}{g(x)} \quad (5)$$

where f and g are functions such that $\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} f(x) = a$ and $\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} g(x) = 0$.

The following proposition would be some help to solving a one type of zero-over-zero form limits such as (1) and (2).

Proposition. Let g be a function such that $\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} g(x) = 0$. Let $n \in \mathbb{N}$, and let $f_1, f_2, \dots, f_n$ be functions such that, for every $k \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$, $\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} f_k(x) = a_k$ and $\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{f_k(x) - a_k}{g(x)}$ exists. Then,

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{f_1(x)f_2(x) \cdots f_n(x) - a_1a_2 \cdots a_n}{g(x)} = \sum_{k=1}^n \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \left(\frac{\prod_{i=1}^n a_i}{a_k} \cdot \frac{f_k(x) - a_k}{g(x)} \right). \quad (6)$$

Proof. For $n \in \mathbb{N}$, we have

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{f_1(x)f_2(x) \cdots f_n(x) - a_1a_2 \cdots a_n}{g(x)} \quad (7)$$

$$= \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{f_1(x)f_2(x) \cdots f_n(x) - a_1a_2 \cdots a_{n-1}f_n(x)}{g(x)} \quad (8)$$

$$+ \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{a_1a_2 \cdots a_{n-1}f_n(x) - a_1a_2 \cdots a_n}{g(x)} \quad (9)$$

$$= \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} f_n(x) \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{f_1(x)f_2(x) \cdots f_{n-1}(x) - a_1a_2 \cdots a_{n-1}}{g(x)} \quad (10)$$

$$+ a_1a_2 \cdots a_{n-1} \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{f_n(x) - a_n}{g(x)} \quad (11)$$

$$= a_n \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{f_1(x)f_2(x) \cdots f_{n-1}(x) - a_1a_2 \cdots a_{n-1}}{g(x)} \quad (12)$$

$$+ \frac{a_1a_2 \cdots a_n}{a_n} \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{f_n(x) - a_n}{g(x)} \quad (13)$$

$$= a_n \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{f_1(x)f_2(x) \cdots f_{n-1}(x) - a_1a_2 \cdots a_{n-2}f_{n-1}(x)}{g(x)} \quad (14)$$

$$+ a_n \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{a_1a_2 \cdots a_{n-2}f_{n-1}(x) - a_1a_2 \cdots a_{n-1}}{g(x)} \quad (15)$$

$$+ \frac{a_1a_2 \cdots a_n}{a_n} \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{f_n(x) - a_n}{g(x)} \quad (16)$$

$$= a_n \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} f_{n-1}(x) \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{f_1(x)f_2(x) \cdots f_{n-2}(x) - a_1a_2 \cdots a_{n-2}}{g(x)} \quad (17)$$

$$+ a_1a_2 \cdots a_{n-2}a_n \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{f_{n-1}(x) - a_{n-1}}{g(x)} + \frac{a_1a_2 \cdots a_n}{a_n} \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{f_n(x) - a_n}{g(x)} \quad (18)$$

$$= a_n a_{n-1} \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{f_1(x)f_2(x) \cdots f_{n-2}(x) - a_1a_2 \cdots a_{n-2}}{g(x)} \quad (19)$$

$$+ \frac{a_1a_2 \cdots a_n}{a_{n-1}} \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{f_{n-1}(x) - a_{n-1}}{g(x)} + \frac{a_1a_2 \cdots a_n}{a_n} \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{f_n(x) - a_n}{g(x)} \quad (20)$$

Repeating the same way as (6), (7) and (12), (13) to this result gives equation which is what we wanted to show. $\square$

Next, we're going to provide some examples.

Example 1. Calculate $L = \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{e^{x^3}(x^2 + 4)^3 - 64}{x^2}$.

$$L = \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{e^{x^3} \cdot (x^2 + 4)^3 - 1 \cdot 4^3}{x^2} = \frac{1 \cdot 4^3}{1} \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{e^{x^3} - 1}{x^2} + \frac{1 \cdot 4^3}{4^3} \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{(x^2 + 4)^3 - 4^3}{x^2} \quad (21)$$

$$= 64 \cdot 0 + 1 \cdot \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{(x^2 + 4)^3 - 64}{x^2} = \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{(x^6 + 12x^4 + 48x^2 + 64) - 64}{x^2} \quad (22)$$

$$= 48 \quad (23)$$

Example 2. Calculate $L = \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{e^{x^3} \cos(2x)(x^2 + 4)^3 - 64}{x^2}$.

$$L = \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{e^{x^3} \cdot \cos(2x) \cdot (x^2 + 4)^3 - 1 \cdot 1 \cdot 4^3}{x^2} \quad (24)$$

$$= \frac{1 \cdot 1 \cdot 4^3}{1} \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{e^{x^3} - 1}{x^2} + \frac{1 \cdot 1 \cdot 4^3}{1} \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{\cos(2x) - 1}{x^2} + \frac{1 \cdot 1 \cdot 4^3}{4^3} \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{(x^2 + 4)^3 - 4^3}{x^2} \quad (25)$$

$$= 64 \cdot \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{e^{x^3} - 1}{x^2} + 64 \cdot \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{\cos(2x) - 1}{x^2} + 1 \cdot \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{(x^2 + 4)^3 - 4^3}{x^2} \quad (26)$$

$$= 64 \cdot 0 + 64 \cdot 4 \cdot \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{\cos(2x) - 1}{(2x)^2} + 1 \cdot \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{(x^6 + 12x^4 + 48x^2 + 64) - 64}{x^2} \quad (27)$$

$$= 256 \cdot \left(-\frac{1}{2}\right) + 1 \cdot 48 \quad (28)$$

$$= -80 \quad (29)$$

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Summary. We consider a way to evaluate a one type of 0/0 form limits as sum of limits.

Reference

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